

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

7 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 3

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№3 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2024-3>

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ISSN: 2181-9297

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EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF MOTIVATION AND PROFICIENCY ON PRAGMALINGUISTIC AWARENESS IN SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNING

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13235224>

ABSTRACT

This study examined how Uzbek students' motivation to learn second languages relates to their comprehension of spoken language, focusing on their awareness of *pragmalinguistic language* usage in diverse contexts. Using *structural equation modeling*, the research investigated these connections. University students participated in video-based roleplay tasks, by transcribing unfamiliar expressions. Various models were tested, revealing unique links between motivation, listening skills, and awareness. The final model underscored a direct association between listening proficiency, academic motivation, and awareness of language nuances, underscoring the importance of listening skills in predicting *pragmalinguistic awareness* over communication-oriented motivation.

Keywords: Pragma linguistic wareness, Second language, Communicative Interaction, Listening Proficiency, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ МОТИВАЦИИ И КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ НА ПРАГМАЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКУЮ ОСОЗНАННОСТЬ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ВТОРОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этом исследовании изучалось, как мотивация узбекских студентов к изучению второго языка связана с их пониманием разговорной речи, при этом основное внимание уделялось их осведомленности о прагмалингвистическом использовании языка в различных контекстах. Используя моделирование структурными уравнениями, исследование исследовало эти связи. Студенты университета участвовали в ролевых играх на основе видео и расшифровывая незнакомые выражения. Были протестированы различные модели, показавшие уникальные связи между мотивацией, навыками слушания и осознанностью. Окончательная модель подчеркнула прямую связь между умением слушать, академической мотивацией и пониманием языковых нюансов, подчеркнув важность навыков слушания в прогнозировании прагмалингвистической осведомленности по сравнению с мотивацией, ориентированной на общение.

Ключевые слова: Прагмалингвистическое осознание, Второй язык, Коммуникативное взаимодействие, Уровень восприятия на слух, Моделирование структурных уравнений (SEM).

IKKINCHI TILNI O'RGANISHDA MOTIVATSIYA VA TIL MALAKASI TA'SIRINING PRAGMALINGVISTIK XABARDORLIK BO'YICHA TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu tadqiqotda o'zbek talabalarining ikkinchi tillarni o'rganishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasi bilan ularning og'zaki tilni tushinishlari qanday bog'liqligi o'rganib chiqildi va ularning turli kontekstlarda pragmalingvistik tildan foydalanish xabardorligiga e'tibor qaratildi. Strukturaviy tenglamalarni modellashtirish usulidan foydalanib, tadqiqot ushbu aloqalarni o'rgandi. Universitet talabarlari notanish iboralarni transkripsiya qilib, videoga asoslangan o'yin topshiriqlarida qatnashdilar. Turli modellar sinovdan o'tkazildi, ular motivatsiya, tinglash qobiliyatlari va xabardorlik o'rtasidagi o'ziga xos aloqalarni ochib berdi. Yakuniy modelda tinglash malakasi, akademik motivatsiya va til nuanslarini bilish o'rtasidagi to'g'ridan-to'g'ri bog'liqlik aniqlanib, muloqotga yo'naltirilgan motivatsiyaga nisbatan pragmalingvistik xabardorlikni tekshirishda tinglash ko'nikmalarining muhimligini ta'kidlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: Pragmalingvistik tushunish, Ikkinchi til, Kommunikativ munosabat, Tinglash malakasi, Struktural tenglamalar modeli (SEM).

INTRODUCTION

There has been an increasing interest in exploring how motivation to learn second languages impacts the development of pragmatic skills in those languages. This study adopts a process-oriented approach to investigate the influence of motivation and proficiency on *pragmalinguistic awareness*, rather than focusing solely on learning outcomes. A key finding was that while certain aspects of motivation were significantly associated with awareness of specific *pragmalinguistic forms*.

In particular, Takahashi (2005) examined whether Japanese EFL learners' motivation to learn English and their proficiency in the language affected their awareness of *pragmalinguistic features* in English request discourse. Building on this, the current study aims to explore the causal links between motivation and proficiency concerning *pragmalinguistic awareness* in implicit pragmatic intervention contexts. To investigate these relationships, three models are proposed and tested using *structural equation modeling (SEM)*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For this research, three sets of materials were prepared. *The first set of materials* consisted of a motivation questionnaire utilized to examine motivation as one of the variables. Some adjustments were made to certain questionnaire items to ensure their relevance for Uzbek students. Each item of the questionnaire was evaluated based on the level of motivation using a five-point scale (1 = Completely disagree; 5 = Completely agree). *The second data collection instrument* was a proficiency measure. The study employed the Secondary Level English Proficiency Test (SLEP), developed by the Educational Testing Service. *The third set of materials* included video dictation (VD) exercises, intended for use in the treatment/awareness session.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The notable influence of listening proficiency on *pragmalinguistic awareness* uncovered in this research is thought-provoking. The findings indicate a mode-specific impact on learners' cognitive processes in second language acquisition. Unlike previous studies that relied on treatment activities emphasizing reading skills, this study incorporated dictation tasks during the treatment phase. Learners' dictation scores, reflecting their cognitive processing loads, were utilized to gauge their awareness of target forms. In essence, students' dictation performance directly influenced the assessment of their awareness, highlighting the integral role of their listening skills. This reconceptualization of awareness may contribute to both proficiency and mode-specific effects [Smith, 2010].

Regarding the impact of proficiency, it was observed that learners engaging in authentic communicative interactions to enhance their second language skills demonstrated higher listening proficiency, rather than the other way around. This progression from "*Communicative Interaction*" to "*Listening Proficiency*" is logical, as such interactions offer learners increased exposure to oral

input. However, it was noted that the indirect influence of “*Communicative Interaction*” on awareness was notably weaker compared to the direct effect of “*Listening Proficiency*”. This indicates that possessing a relatively high level of listening proficiency, which facilitates accurate dictation of target words, is more critical for learners to recognize bi-clausal request forms than their motivation driven by communication. These findings underscore the challenge students` face in noticing target forms in authentic communicative contexts unless they possess sufficiently high listening proficiency and the ability to selectively attend to second language input.

Additionally, the study found that learners who prioritize and enjoy classroom activities were more adept at detecting the target bi-clausal forms. These learners are anticipated to derive maximum benefit from classroom materials. In this study, the intensive dictation exercises were designed to convince learners that these materials would significantly enhance their listening proficiency. Furthermore, learners inclined toward classroom activities may inherently find such gap-filling tasks engaging. The dictation materials in this study may have been compelling enough for these learners to focus on the tasks, thereby facilitating the recognition of target forms. This suggests that awareness of target forms may be more achievable or efficient in classroom environments than in authentic communicative situations if the objectives of classroom activities are clear, and the input is meaningfully manipulated through relevant materials for purposeful activities [Brown, 2015].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the current investigation delved into the interplay between students` motivation, listening skills, and their grasp of complex bi-clausal request structures. Twenty Uzbek students participated in the study, wherein three hypothesized structural models were tested using *Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)*. Through the application of goodness-of-fit statistics, a final structural model was chosen as the most suitable for the data at hand. This model endorsed a fundamental causal framework where students` communication-oriented motivation directly influenced their listening proficiency, subsequently impacting their awareness of *pragmalinguistic nuances*, the focal variable in the model. Notably, the direct influence of listening proficiency on awareness outweighed the indirect impact of communication-oriented motivation. Thus, enhancing students` listening skills should be prioritized in instructional settings to enable efficient processing of second language input and accurate identification of target forms. Additionally, the selected structural model revealed a direct link between students` class-oriented motivation and their awareness of target forms. These findings imply that fostering students` *pragmalinguistic awareness* could hinge on educators` endeavors to create engaging and meaningful classroom activities and materials, aimed at optimizing second language proficiency. Despite these insights, further exploration of additional variables is warranted in future research to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of *pragmalinguistic awareness*. Moreover, ongoing investigation within the realm of linguistics is essential to advance this line of inquiry.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 3

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